

CERTIFICATE OF PUBLICATION

We Acknowledge the Manuscript entitled
Phishing Attack Detection for Small Organisations – Using Machine Learning

Submitted by

Mr. Ayan Ghosh

has been published in

Journal of Advanced Research in Artificial Intelligence & It's Applications

Volume 02 Issue 03 Year 2025

*With regards,
Poonam Barla
Publication Team
HBRP Publication Pvt. Ltd.*